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“IS MULTILINGUALISM A STRENGTH OR A STRUGGLE?”

The Philippines is one of the countries known to be rich with languages being spoken by its people. In fact, there are about 180 or more languages that are actively used across the nation. This qualifies the country to be considered a multilingual nation. Being a multilingual country, the Filipinos grow up navigating an environment rich with languages that were shaped or influenced by history, culture, and colonization. Despite these diversified languages, the country still grapples with a pressing question, if multilingualism does really enhance or hinder the English proficiency among Filipino learners.

Bulk of research shows that multilingualism can enhance cognitive, flexibility, problem-solving skills, and intercultural understanding. Thus, it might be possible that learners, who grow up in a multilingual household or environment where switching from varied languages such as Ilocano, Kankanaey, Ibaloi, Filipino or English is a practice demonstrate strong adaptive communication skills. In considering various languages spoken in a community, whether in school, at work or at home, I do believe that there's no language better than others. As an English teacher, I do not view that English is superior to other languages. People have their own language ideologies, depending on what they perceive is more important or beneficial. I respect that. Regarding ideology, English, is still often regarded as the “language of success,” and it remains deeply associated with intelligence, prestige, and economic opportunity. This ideology has positioned English as both a gatekeeper and a goal in schools, workplaces, and even in social status. This belief has somehow influenced some Filipino parents to train their kids to speak in English and for some, it becomes their first language.

As a parent, I am an influential factor to the language of my kids. I let my first two use English as their first language considering that most of the subjects are taught in English. In this sense, I had thought that it will help them to understand and perform better in the varied subjects especially in Science and Mathematics; yes, indeed, speaking well in English could be an edge or advantage. However, I observed that there are also negative implications especially on their social interactions with other kids in the neighborhood. As a result, I ended up introducing Ilocano and some Filipino words when they turned four or five. Also, through observation among my students who are monolingual, I noticed that they are not actively involved in classroom and school activities. Most of the students who are academically and co-curricular achievers are not monolingual. They often speak various languages. Because of this, I exposed my third child to varied languages as early as one. However, regardless of the positive results on what multilingualism brings as reiterated by many studies, challenges remain to be encountered by teachers in an English classroom. Students still struggle in expressing complex ideas in English despite the fact that English has been part of instruction since pre-school. Also, despite this common move among parents, a question that educators

encounter inside the classroom is that, “Why can’t students express their thoughts well compared to the past days when parents trained their kids with their mother tongue and English was learned formally in school instead of acquiring it?”

Multilingualism can really aid a student to express himself or herself inside the classroom, but it may also invite him or her to engage in code-switching or mixing. Yes, this is acceptable knowing that the Philippines is a bilingual country. Aside from that, the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) policy of 2012 was also crafted to promote the use of local languages in the early years of schooling among learners. While these policies aim to improve literacy and cultural identity, some groups argue that it delays English acquisition and may affect the overall competence of students. Yes, I personally believe that it may also limit grammatical accuracy and vocabulary development in the English language.

Based on varied studies, English proficiency among Filipino students has shown a gradual decline, particularly in reading comprehension and writing. The study attributes this partly to inconsistent language use in schools and inadequate teacher training in multilingual instruction. This concern posts if multilingualism is really a strength or struggle. In which specific area is considered gray when it comes to the openness to multilingualism inside the classroom?

As the Philippines continues to embrace multilingualism, the education sector must revisit how language policies are implemented on the ground. Investing in teacher development, designing context-based English programs, and promoting positive attitudes toward local languages can help bridge the gap.

Thus, the goal of multilingualism in the country is not to totally lessen interaction in English inside the classroom but to create a multilingual generation, capable of thinking, learning and connecting using varied languages, without losing competence in any. Now, is multilingualism a strength or struggle? What do you think?

